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Multifunctional Surface Coatings: Antimicrobial, Anti-Fouling and Anticorrosive Strategies Based on Biopolymers and Functional Modifications

David Estevez^{1*}, Ivan Cangas¹, Angie Inga¹, and Raul Davalos Monteiro¹

¹School of Biological Sciences and Engineering, Yachay Tech University, Urucuquí, 100119, Ecuador

Abstract

Biomedical coatings with multifunctional properties have been important in improving the safety, durability, and performance of implantable medical devices. This review focuses on three main types of coatings, highlighting their mechanisms, materials, and biomedical relevance. Antimicrobial coatings use agents such as silver nanoparticles, nitric oxide donors, or chitosan to inhibit bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation. Anti-fouling coatings, such as those based on PEG and zwitterionic polymers, reduce protein and cell adhesion through hydration barriers and electrostatic repulsion. Anti-corrosion coatings, such as diamond-like carbon, metal oxides, and bioceramics, protect metal implants from chemical degradation and ion release. Various deposition techniques such as PVD, CVD, sol-gel, and layer by layer assembly are analyzed, considering their advantages and limitations in terms of adhesion, uniformity, and functionality. In addition, performance metrics, biocompatibility, sterilization compatibility, and regulatory requirements are discussed. This highlights emerging trends toward smart, bio-inspired coatings with controlled release and adaptive behavior.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, Anti-Fouling, Anticorrosive, Surface coatings, Biopolymers

1 Introduction

Surfaces exposed to biological or environmental fluids often face severe challenges such as microbial contamination, biofilm formation, and corrosion. These phenomena not only degrade material performance but also represent a major cause of implant failure, hospital-acquired infections, and economic losses in the biomedical and industrial sectors. Antimicrobial coatings incorporate biocidal agents for example, silver nanoparticles or NO donors—that eliminate pathogens. In fact, silver nanoparticles in coatings can inhibit a wide range of microorganisms and prevent the formation of biofilms. Antifouling coatings create ultrahydrophilic or balanced-charge surfaces (e.g., PEGylated polymers or zwitterionic materials) that generate a strong hydration layer, hindering the initial adhesion of proteins and microbial cells. Finally, anticorrosive coatings form protective barriers on implantable metals to prevent chemical degradation [Dávalos Monteiro \(2021\)](#). For example, in biodegradable magnesium alloy coronary stents, a polymer composite coating has been shown to significantly reduce the corrosion rate and improve the resistance to degradation in vitro [Dube and Okuthe \(2025\)](#)[Andreeva and et al. \(2024\)](#). Recent research explores various materials and strategies, such as silver, chitosan, pegylation, zwitterionic polymers, and nitric oxide (NO) release, to enhance the safety and longevity of devices.

The biomedical relevance of these coatings lies in their application in implantable devices and clinical surfaces. For example, silver is valued for its broad antimicrobial activity, acting by the sustained release of Ag ions, which penetrate the walls of microbial cells and disrupt multiple internal functions. Chitosan, a cationic polymer derived from chitin, has its own antimicrobial activity; by electrostatic adhering to negatively charged bacterial membranes, it causes cell permeabilization and lysis. Furthermore, when combined with antimicrobial peptides or other polymers, chitosan generates coatings with improved efficacy and good biocompatibility. However, PEGylated surfaces and zwitterionic polymers work by creating a strongly bound layer of water

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*Corresponding author
luis.estevez@yachaytech.edu.ec

(hydration layer) that prevents the attachment of proteins and cells, thus reducing the development of biofilms. Finally, NO-releasing surfaces exploit the antimicrobial action of this gas: NO is a broad-spectrum antibacterial agent whose mechanism is not affected by bacterial resistance. Its controlled release from a coating can penetrate and disrupt biofilms and also confer valuable antithrombotic properties in cardiovascular devices. Dube and Okuthe (2025) Teixeira-Santos et al. (2021) Qian et al. (2022)

To overcome these challenges, biomedical coatings have emerged as surface layers engineered to improve compatibility, prevent infection, control degradation, impart specific biological functions, and enhance device functionality. Recent advances focus on multifunctional coatings that combine antimicrobial, antifouling, and anticorrosion properties, effectively reducing bacterial accumulation and surface deterioration. Zander and Becker (2018) Teixeira-Santos et al. (2021)

This review aims to summarize current developments, mechanisms, and design strategies for these next-generation coatings that improve the durability and clinical safety of biomedical devices,

2 Classification of Biomedical Coatings and Mechanisms

As is well known, coatings are layers, and in the biomedical field, they also serve as layers in various biomaterials with different functions, such as implants and biomedical devices, among others. These coatings play a very important role in increasing or optimizing the performance based on the properties of these biomaterials to achieve a more efficient effect within the body. One of the main functions of this type of coating is to prevent infections, reduce unwanted adhesion of proteins and cells, and protect against corrosion of the base material, which is common, which is crucial for the safety and durability of medical devices (Busscher et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2020). This is very important since the interaction between the surface and the biological environment is fundamental to determining the effectiveness of the coating, including factors such as bacterial adhesion, immune response, and tissue integration (Ramakrishna et al., 2015).

When referring to strategies for developing biomedical coatings, it should be noted that there are many ways to do so, but the main one is based on specific mechanisms of action. A clear example is when some coatings release antimicrobial ions or active molecules that inhibit bacterial growth, increasing the proliferation of bacteria in the medium, while others create physical or chemical barriers that prevent biofilm adhesion without directly affecting microorganisms (Liu et al., 2019). Similarly, certain coatings can be said to protect metallic materials from corrosion under physiological conditions, ensuring long-term chemical and mechanical stability, as is the case with heart implants, where this is very common (Ratner et al., 2013).

For this study, we decided to apply a systematic classification of these coatings. This allows us to compare their properties, mechanisms of action, and clinical applications to better identify the ease of selection based on the needs of the medical device and the appropriate physiological conditions for the intended application. Furthermore, this classification is key to identifying areas where new solutions, coating combinations, or innovations are required to overcome current limitations in biocompatibility, sterilization, and durability (Chen et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2019).

2.1 Main classification of coatings

2.1.1 Antimicrobial coatings

One of the main problems presented by implants associated with medical devices is that they represent a critical issue in clinical practice and biomedical validation, causing serious complications and resulting in excessive hospital stays Campoccia et al. (2013). This is why antimicrobial coatings are very important, as they are designed to prevent bacterial colonization and biofilm formation, one of the factors that hinders treatment with systemic antibiotics. These coatings allow implants to maintain their functionality while preventing microbial proliferation at the biomaterial-tissue interface Hetrick and Schoenfisch (2006).

The process of developing these types of coatings has evolved from simple antibiotic impregnation strategies to multifunctional coatings, which are very important in the field of drug delivery because they combine controlled release of active agents with physical properties that hinder bacterial adhesion and at the same time help deliver a more targeted treatment. However, to

apply these types of coatings, a basic protocol must be followed: the selection of an appropriate coating depends on the type of device, the anatomy of the implant site, and the characteristics of the most common pathogens associated with nosocomial infections, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Rai et al. (2012).

2.1.2 Types and Mechanisms of Action

Metallic Coatings

Specific metals have been widely applied in microbial activity, such as silver, copper, and zinc. Silver, for its part, is highly effective against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, fungi, and some viruses. This is because the main mechanism is based on the controlled release of Ag ions, which interact with the cell membrane of these bacteria, essential proteins, and bacterial DNA, causing cell death and biofilm inhibition, which is essential for the coating action Rai et al. (2012); Chen et al. (2020).

Metallic coatings can be applied using various techniques such as Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) or electrodeposition, which allow control of thickness, uniformity, and ion release, critical factors for maximizing antimicrobial efficacy and allowing for more specific biomedical application needs, without inducing cytotoxicity in human cells Liu et al. (2014). Common applications include orthopedic implants, catheters, and coated stents, where preventing early bacterial colonization is crucial to reducing the incidence of infections, which can cause problems for patients receiving the coating.

Coatings based on active molecules

On the other hand, we must also understand that there is another strategy that consists of incorporating antimicrobial agents directly onto the surface of the implant or biomaterial being used, allowing for controlled local release. This includes antibiotics such as gentamicin, vancomycin, or coatings that release nitric oxide (NO), an endogenous molecule with potent antimicrobial and inflammation-modulating activity Hetrick and Schoenfisch (2006).

In essence, it can be said that this mechanism is based on the sustained release of these molecules directly at the implantation site of this type of implant, which increases the local concentration against pathogens without producing significant systemic effects. Furthermore, we can find other systems that combine chemical release with physical anti-adhesive properties, achieving a double barrier against biofilm and therefore bacterial colonization. This approach has been used in catheters, advanced dressings, and certain orthopedic implants with a high risk of infection.

Natural polymers with antimicrobial activity

Within this group of coatings, we also find natural polymers, such as chitosan. These are very important as they represent a biocompatible and biodegradable alternative. Their antimicrobial mechanism is based on electrostatic interactions with bacterial membranes, which alters permeability and causes cell lysis Rabea et al. (2003). Furthermore, they can form films on the implant surface that hinder the adhesion of bacteria and proteins, contributing to an indirect anti-fouling effect.

It is important to mention that chitosan is used both alone and in combination with metallic nanoparticles or antibiotics, enhancing its effectiveness against resistant biofilms. It has been applied in orthopedic prostheses, coated stents, and dressings, and is notable for its safety and modulating effect on the local immune response. We can see all this in a comparison through the table 1 that compares these methodologies

Figure 1. Antimicrobial coatings and their mechanisms of action. (a) Metallic coatings release antimicrobial metal ions (Ag, Cu², Zn²). (b) Active molecule coatings provide local antibiotic or nitric oxide release. (c) Chitosan coatings act via electrostatic interactions.

Figure 1 illustrates the main types and mechanisms of antimicrobial coatings used in biomedical applications. These coatings are designed to prevent bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation on implant surfaces. Metallic coatings act through the controlled release of antimicrobial ions (Ag, Cu², Zn²), active molecule coatings provide localized delivery of antibiotics or nitric oxide, and natural polymer coatings such as chitosan exert their effect via electrostatic disruption of bacterial membranes.

Table 1. Comparison of antimicrobial coatings and their clinical applications.

Coating type	Mechanism of action	Examples	Clinical applications
Metallic	Ion release that damages membrane, proteins, and DNA	Silver, copper, zinc	Orthopedic implants, catheters, stents
Active molecules	Local release of antibiotics or NO	Gentamicin, vancomycin, NO-releasing	Catheters, dressings, orthopedic implants
Natural polymers	Electrostatic interaction disrupting membranes, physical barrier formation	Chitosan, chitosan + nanoparticles	Prostheses, dressings, stents

¹ NO: Nitric oxide.

² Effectiveness may vary depending on concentration, surface modification, and clinical environment.

2.2 Anti-fouling coatings

One of the most important coatings in this area is anti-fouling coatings, which are essential for minimizing the adhesion of proteins, cells, and microorganisms to implants and various medical devices. This is particularly important here, as it is known that the initial protein adsorption characteristic can trigger bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation, hindering biomaterial integration and increasing the risk of medical device-associated infections Prime and Whitesides (1991); Zhang et al. (2019a). Viewed from the perspective of antimicrobial coatings, which seek to directly kill or inhibit microorganisms, anti-fouling coatings act by preventing initial colonization through physical and chemical barriers, acting as a preventive defense mechanism, helping to maintain the biocompatibility and long-term functionality of the implant and its application. Something

very important to mention is that the design of these coatings is based on chemical and physical modifications of the surface, including the incorporation of hydrophilic polymers, zwitterionic groups, and micro/nanostructures that alter surface energy. These strategies seek to maintain two important characteristics: a hydrated environment and a neutral environment, reducing the interaction of biomolecules and cells with the surface without interfering with tissue integration Chen et al. (2010).

2.2.1 Types and Mechanisms of Action

PEGylation (polyethylene glycol)

PEGylation is a very important technique that involves the covalent attachment of polyethylene glycol (PEG) chains to the surface of the biomaterial being treated. These chains create a steric hydration layer that will somehow prevent proteins and cells from getting close enough to adhere Prime and Whitesides (1991); Zhang et al. (2019a). This mechanism is based on physical repulsion and the steric exclusion effect, which remains stable even in the presence of complex plasma proteins.

These types of coatings are very important as they are widely used in catheters, biosensors, dialysis membranes, and other devices exposed to bodily fluids. It is essential to consider the density and length of the PEG chains, as this determines the anti-fouling efficacy. It can be said that longer and denser chains provide a better barrier, although they require more controlled deposition techniques such as self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) or plasma grafting Liu et al. (2014).

Zwitterionic Coatings

On the other hand, zwitterionic coatings contain functional groups with both positive and negative charges, which is very important as this helps maintain an overall neutral net charge. This generates a highly stable hydrated layer that repels proteins and cells through electrostatic interactions and steric repulsion Chen et al. (2010).

Unlike PEGylation, zwitterions have a key characteristic: they are more resistant to oxidation and degradation in physiological environments, making them suitable for implants that will be used for extended periods, such as coronary stents, orthopedic implants, and implantable microchips. Furthermore, these coatings can reduce complement protein activation and the local inflammatory response, which is important since it is the most aggressive response, contributing to improved biological tolerance of the device.

Superhydrophilic or superhydrophobic surfaces

Something extremely important to mention in this work is the extreme modification of surface wettability, which is another anti-fouling strategy. Superhydrophilic surfaces form a stable water layer that hinders protein and cell contact, while superhydrophobic surfaces repel biomolecules thanks to micro/nanostructures that reduce the effective contact area Falde et al. (2016).

These surfaces have been widely used in various biomedical applications such as catheters, cardiovascular implants, and drug delivery devices, showing significant reductions in biofilm formation in *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. The choice between superhydrophilic or superhydrophobic surfaces depends on the specific application.

Figure 2. Anti-fouling coatings and their mechanisms. (a) PEGylation coatings form hydrated steric barriers that repel proteins and cells. (b) Zwitterionic coatings create neutral, highly hydrated layers resistant to fouling and inflammation. (c) Superhydrophilic or superhydrophobic surfaces modify surface energy to minimize microbial or protein adhesion.

Figure 2 summarizes the main mechanisms of anti-fouling coatings.

Table 2. Comparison of anti-fouling coatings and their clinical applications.

Coating type	Mechanism of action	Examples	Clinical applications
PEGylation	Steric hydration layer reducing biomolecule adhesion	Polyethylene glycol (PEG)	Catheters, biosensors, dialysis membranes
Zwitterionic	Hydrated neutral-charge layer repelling proteins and cells	Sulfobetaine, carboxybetaine	Orthopedic implants, stents, implantable microchips
Superhydrophilic / Superhydrophobic	Physical and chemical repulsion of biomolecules via micro/nanostructures	TiO ₂ , SiO ₂ with nano-patterned surfaces	Catheters, cardiovascular implants, drug delivery devices

¹ PEG: Polyethylene glycol.

² Micro/nanostructures enhance the antifouling effect by altering surface topography and wettability.

In this way, Table 2 provides a comparative summary of anti-fouling coatings, showing how different physicochemical surface modifications can prevent biofouling and improve the safety and functionality of biomedical devices.

2.3 Anti-corrosion coatings

When we refer to the corrosion of metallic materials in the physiological environment or its relationship with biomedical implants and related applications, it represents a significant challenge for the durability and safety of implants. Metals such as the classic ones found in the literature for biomedical applications, such as titanium, stainless steel, and cobalt-chromium alloys, although widely used, can suffer degradation due to exposure to ions and proteins present in body fluids or physiological variations that are very common within the body. This leads to the release of metal ions that can cause local or systemic toxicity and compromise the mechanical integrity of the implant and its function [Ratner et al. \(2013\)](#).

When we refer to anti-corrosion coatings, they act as physical and chemical barriers, protecting the base material and prolonging the life and usefulness of these coatings in biomedical devices. One of the key characteristics for the application of these coatings is based on specific properties. These coatings can be biocompatible and bioactive. The key is that these properties must meet certain objectives, such as osseointegration or hemocompatibility, depending on the application. However, one of the major challenges is that the selection of the coating depends on the type of metal, the physiological environment (pH, chloride concentration), and the function of the

implant (orthopedic, dental, cardiovascular). We can see all this in a comparison through table 1 that compares these methodologies.

2.3.1 Types and Mechanisms of Action

Diamond-like carbon (DLC)

- Thin films of amorphous carbon with mechanical and chemical properties similar to diamond.
- Regarding the mechanisms according to the literature, these form a very hard physical and stable chemical barrier that reduces the interaction of the metal with the physiological environment to prevent damage to biomedical devices, preventing the release of metal ions and corrosion [Grill \(1999\)](#).
- Among their most common applications are orthopedic prostheses, dental implants, stent components, and heart valves.

Metal Oxide Coatings

- These are films of oxides such as TiO, AlO, or ZrO on metal surfaces.
- Mechanistically, we know that these act as a passive chemical barrier, reducing electron transfer and electrochemical corrosion. Some oxides are also photocatalytic or bioactive, promoting osseointegration [Hanawa \(2011\)](#).
- The most important applications are orthopedic and dental implants, internal fixations, and surgical instruments.

Ceramic and Bioceramic Coatings

- These are layers of hydroxyapatite (HA), calcium phosphates, or bioactive glass applied to metals.
- To understand their mechanism, it is important to understand that they form a chemical and physical barrier, and in some cases, they interact with bone tissue to improve integration. Hydroxyapatite protects the metal from corrosive physiological fluids and simultaneously promotes osseointegration [Dorozhkin \(2010\)](#).
- They are common in orthopedic implants, joint prosthesis coatings, and bone fixation screws. Tabla comparativa: Recubrimientos anticorrosion

When referring to the corrosion of metallic materials in physiological environments, it represents a significant challenge for the durability and safety of biomedical implants. Metals such as titanium, stainless steel, and cobalt-chromium alloys, although widely used, can suffer degradation due to exposure to ions and proteins present in body fluids. This degradation leads to the release of metallic ions that may cause local or systemic toxicity, compromising the mechanical integrity and biocompatibility of the implant [Ratner et al. \(2013\)](#). Anti-corrosion coatings act as physical and chemical barriers that protect the base metal and extend the functional lifetime of implants.

(a) Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC)

(b) Metal oxide coatings (TiO₂, Al₂O₃, ZrO₂)

(c) Ceramic / Bioceramic coatings (Hydroxyapatite / CaP)

Figure 3. Anti-corrosion coatings and their mechanisms. (a) Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC) forms a dense and inert physical barrier that blocks ion diffusion and corrosion. (b) Metal oxide coatings act as passive chemical barriers that reduce electron transfer and can also promote bioactivity. (c) Bioceramic coatings provide both corrosion resistance and biological integration by releasing Ca²⁺ and PO₄³⁻ ions to stimulate bone bonding.

Figure 3 illustrates the main mechanisms of anti-corrosion coatings used in biomedical applications.

Table 3. Comparison of anticorrosion and bioceramic coatings with clinical applications.

Coating type	Mechanism of action	Examples	Clinical applications
Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC)	Hard physical barrier with stable chemistry that prevents ion diffusion	DLC	Orthopedic prostheses, dental implants, stents
Metal oxides	Passive chemical barrier, sometimes bioactive and photocatalytic	TiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , ZrO ₂	Orthopedic implants, surgical instruments, dental coatings
Ceramics / Bioceramics	Chemical and physical barrier promoting osseointegration through Ca ²⁺ and PO ₄ ³⁻ release	Hydroxyapatite, calcium phosphates, bioactive glasses	Joint prostheses, bone screws, dental coatings

¹ DLC: Diamond-Like Carbon.

² Hydroxyapatite and other calcium phosphates enhance bone integration and implant stability.

In this way, Table 3 provides a comparative overview of anti-corrosion and bioceramic coatings, highlighting their mechanisms, composition, and biomedical applications.

Classification of Deposition Techniques

Deposition techniques for antimicrobial, antifouling, and anticorrosive coatings can be broadly classified into three major categories physical methods, chemical/wet chemistry methods, and advanced/emerging methods.

First of all, there are physical methods such as Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD). This includes sputtering, thermal evaporation, and plasma-assisted methods. Sputtering and evaporation are the most common, allowing for high-purity, adherent, and uniform thin films for metals, ceramics, and alloys. Plasma sputtering-physical vapor deposition (PS-PVD) combines thermal sputtering and vapor deposition, allowing for customized microstructures and coatings without a line of sight. Mahyoub et al. (2025) Lu et al. (2023)

Chemical and wet chemistry methods such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD), which uses volatile precursors to form solid films on substrates, sol-gel, electrodeposition, dip coating, spin coating, and layer-by-layer (LbL) coating are solution-based methods that enable uniform, large-area coatings at low cost. Zhang et al. (2023) Yaseen et al. (2023)

In addition to advanced or emerging techniques such as electrospinning, which are useful for functional coatings. Atomic layer deposition (ALD) is ideal for 3D nanostructures and advanced barrier coatings. Yaseen et al. (2023)

Each class offers unique advantages in terms of film quality, scalability, and compatibility with different materials and substrates. In this context table 5 represents a comparison of deposition/fabrication methods, advantages, and trade-offs for multifunctional biomedical coatings.

3 Performance and Comparative Metrics

Biomedical coatings must be evaluated and compared using performance metrics that consider both their physical characteristics and biofunctional outcomes. Adhesion strength is a key parameter, as high adherence prevents delamination that could expose the substrate or release debris. Adhesion is typically measured through scratch, pull-off, and tape tests, following standards such as ASTM D4541 Butler (2023). For example, hydroxyapatite coatings applied by plasma spraying must adhere to metallic substrates with strengths above 15 MPa. Deposition techniques like PVD or CVD provide excellent adhesion via metallurgical bonding or interdiffusion at the interface, whereas dip- or spray-cast coatings often require surface priming or crosslinking. A polymer-bioactive glass nanocoating fabricated via a laser-sol-gel route showed excellent adhesion and peeling resistance, forming an effective anti-corrosion barrier. Surface preparation steps, such as roughening or applying primers, enhance mechanical interlocking and chemical bonding Negut et al. (2024).

Surface roughness is another critical metric influencing biological responses. Micro- and nanoscale topographies modulate protein adsorption and cell behavior: moderate roughness increases surface area and protein binding, while nanoscale features may inhibit bacterial adhesion by creating unfavorable attachment conditions. Roughness also affects wear; for example, a rough coating on a hip implant can increase counter-surface wear. Plasma-sprayed hydroxyapatite coatings with micrometer-scale roughness promote bone in-growth but are unsuitable for articulating surfaces Shea (2025). Wettability, quantified through water contact angle, determines surface energy and strongly affects protein adsorption, bacterial attachment, and cellular interactions. Hydrophilic surfaces (low contact angles) facilitate water spreading and hydration layer formation, improving antifouling performance and reducing protein adsorption. Hemocompatibility is essential for coatings on blood-contacting devices such as stents, catheters, and vascular grafts. Relevant metrics include coagulation times, complement activation, and platelet adhesion Nilawar et al. (2021b). Platelet adhesion assays expose coated surfaces to platelet-rich plasma, count adherent platelets, and assess morphology. Hemocompatible coatings exhibit fewer, round, and inactive platelets. For instance, PEGDMA-based coatings minimize platelet activation and significantly reduce fibrinogen adsorption. Table 6 summarizes representative antifouling and hemocompatibility metrics comparing PEGylated/zwitterionic brush-coated surfaces with controls.

Table 5. Comparison of deposition/fabrication methods, advantages, and trade-offs for multifunctional biomedical coatings.

Method	Advantages	Trade-offs	Cite
Thermal Spray	Low cost, high deposition rate, strong adhesion, scalable.	Non-uniformity, line-of-sight only, amorphous coatings, less control over microstructure.	Huang et al. (2024); Bharadishettar et al. (2021)
Electrodeposition / Electroless	Uniform coatings, low temperature, suitable for complex geometries, tunable morphology.	Poor tear strength, adhesion issues, environmental disposal of baths, costly for pure metals.	Owhal et al. (2021); Mamgain et al. (2024)
PVD / CVD (Physical / Chemical Vapor Deposition)	Thin, adherent, durable layers; precise control of thickness and composition; allows functionally graded coatings.	Expensive equipment, limited nanoporous control, potential contamination from volatile gases.	Tian et al. (2023) Bharadishettar et al. (2021)
Sol-Gel / Dip Coating	Simple, eco-friendly, suitable for embedding nanoparticles; good for antifouling and corrosion resistance.	Limited mechanical durability, may require post-treatment (e.g., heat curing).	Ielo et al. (2021) Zhang et al. (2019b) Zhang et al. (2021)
Layer-by-Layer (LbL) Assembly	Highly versatile; enables multifunctionality (antimicrobial, antifouling, anticorrosive); customizable architecture.	Time-consuming, may require crosslinking or post-treatment for long-term stability.	Li et al. (2019)
Electrophoretic Deposition	Simple setup, good for composite coatings, allows tailored drug loading and release profiles.	Limited to charged particles; may require post-processing for adhesion or densification.	Kumar et al. (2015)
Polymer / Nanocomposite Blending	Scalable; combines hydrophobicity, antifouling, and corrosion resistance; adaptable to multiple substrates.	May require complex synthesis; long-term stability and uniformity may vary.	Chen et al. (2019); Nguyen et al. (2021); Patel et al. (2017); Wang et al. (2019)

¹ Abbreviations: PVD – Physical Vapor Deposition; CVD – Chemical Vapor Deposition; LbL – Layer-by-Layer assembly.

² Selection of method depends on application needs (e.g., biomedical implants, antimicrobial coatings, or anticorrosion layers).

Table 6. Antifouling and hemocompatibility metrics

Variables	JKL (<i>n</i> = 30)	Control (<i>n</i> = 40)	MN	<i>t</i> (68)
Water contact angle (°)	32	78	-46.0	-12.4
Fibrinogen adsorption (ng/cm ²)	8.5	120.0	-111.5	-15.2
Albumin adsorption (ng/cm ²)	5.2	95.0	-89.8	-14.1
Platelet adhesion (cells/mm ²)	120	4200	-4080	-10.8
Biofilm coverage 24 h (%) ²	3.2	48.5	-45.3	-13.0
Hemolysis (%)	0.3	0.8	-0.5	-3.1

¹ JKL, PEGylated/zwitterionic brush-coated 316L coupons (antifouling surface).

² MN, mean difference (JKL–Control); negative values favor JKL (lower is better).

For antimicrobial and anticorrosion performance, electrochemical and microbiological parameters provide a robust evaluation framework. Potentiodynamic polarization is used to measure corrosion current density and potential, while electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) assesses coating resistance. Effective anticorrosion coatings lower corrosion current densities by several orders of magnitude and increase the pitting potential of metals. A bare magnesium alloy, for instance, may exhibit a corrosion current of 50 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ in simulated body fluid, whereas a polymer/ceramic-coated version can reduce this to 1 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$. Similarly, impedance at low frequencies may increase from $10^3 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ to $10^6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ following coating application. Immersion tests over extended periods are also common, measuring metal ion release or weight loss between coated and uncoated samples. Table 7 illustrates typical antimicrobial and anticorrosion results for an Ag–chitosan (Ag–CS) composite coating compared to a control surface.

Table 7. Antimicrobial efficacy and anticorrosion performance

Variables	JKL (<i>n</i> = 30)	Control (<i>n</i> = 40)	MN	<i>t</i> (68)
Bacterial load 24 h, <i>S. aureus</i> (log ₁₀ CFU/cm ²)	1.8	5.9	-4.1	-11.7
Biofilm biomass (OD ₅₉₀)	0.12	0.78	-0.66	-9.5
Zone of inhibition (mm)	10.4	0.0	+10.4	+8.7
Corrosion current i_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	0.95	6.80	-5.85	-7.9
$ Z _{0.01 \text{ Hz}}$ ($\text{k}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	165	12	+153	+9.8
Adhesion strength (MPa) ²	22.5	18.3	+4.2	+3.4

¹ JKL, Ag–chitosan (Ag–CS) composite dip-coated on 316L stainless steel.

² MN, mean difference (JKL–Control); positive values favor JKL when “higher is better.”

A comprehensive summary of the most important performance metrics, their relevance, measurement techniques, and typical target values is provided in Table 8.

4 Safety, Sterilization, and Regulatory Considerations

When developing and implementing biomedical coatings, it is crucial to address their safety profile, compatibility with sterilization processes, and compliance with regulatory requirements. Even coatings that demonstrate excellent laboratory performance must satisfy these practical considerations to achieve clinical translation and regulatory approval.

4.1 Biocompatibility and Toxicity

The first step in safety is to make sure a coating doesn’t cause any negative biological reactions. According to ISO 10993 guidelines, this entails cytotoxicity testing, evaluations of irritation and sensitization, and longer-term biocompatibility studies. For instance, excessive silver ion release can be cytotoxic and result in argyria or local tissue damage, hence silver-based antimicrobial coatings need to be carefully developed. The size and surface chemistry of silver nanoparticles

Table 8. Key performance metrics for biomedical coatings (antimicrobial, antifouling, and anticorrosion).

Metric	Definition / Relevance	Measurement Techniques	Typical Target Values
Adhesion Strength (MPa)	Force required to detach coating from substrate; critical for long-term stability and durability.	Scratch test, pull-off test, tape test (ASTM D4541)	>15 MPa (HA), >20 MPa (polymer/metal)
Surface Roughness (R_a , nm– μ m)	Micro/nano topography influencing cell behavior, protein adsorption, and bacterial adhesion.	Profilometry, AFM, SEM image analysis	10–500 nm (vascular), 1–50 μ m (orthopedic)
Wettability (Contact Angle, $^\circ$)	Surface hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity affecting protein adsorption and antifouling.	Static water contact angle measurement	Hydrophilic: < 40 $^\circ$ (PEG, zwitterionic); Superhydrophobic: > 150 $^\circ$
Protein Adsorption (ng/cm ²)	Amount of plasma proteins bound; lower values indicate superior antifouling.	QCM-D, ellipsometry, fluorescent tagging	<10 ng/cm ² (PEG/zwitterionic)
Biofilm Formation (% surface coverage)	Indicator of antimicrobial/antifouling efficacy; lower coverage reflects better performance.	Crystal violet assay, CFU counting, CLSM	>90% reduction vs. control
Hemocompatibility (cells/mm ²)	Measures thrombogenic potential of blood-contacting surfaces.	Platelet adhesion assays, SEM, clotting time (PTT)	<500 cells/mm ² , prolonged PTT
Osteointegration (Bone-implant contact, %)	Evaluates bonding and tissue integration for orthopedic/dental applications.	Histomorphometry, push-out tests, ALP activity	>70% BIC after 8 weeks
Corrosion Resistance (i_{corr} , μ A/cm ²)	Current density indicating corrosion rate; lower = better protection.	Potentiodynamic polarization, EIS	<1 μ A/cm ² , impedance >10 ⁶ Ω ·cm ²
Cytotoxicity (Cell viability, %)	Biocompatibility and safety of coating components.	MTT, Live/Dead assay, ISO 10993 tests	>90% viability
In Vivo Performance (Infection rate, %)	Clinical relevance: infection prevention, healing, and integration.	Animal models, histology, microbiological analysis	Infection reduction >95% vs. control

¹ BIC: Bone-implant contact; QCM-D: Quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation.

² Target values vary with application; vascular coatings prioritize hemocompatibility, orthopedic coatings prioritize osteointegration.

are two important physicochemical characteristics that affect their biocompatibility [Bäumler et al. \(2022\)](#). Safety profiles can be enhanced by optimization techniques such surface changes and controlled ion release.

4.2 Sterilization Compatibility

All medical devices must undergo sterilization before clinical use, and coatings must retain their functionality and integrity post-sterilization. Common sterilization methods include autoclaving (steam, 121–134 °C), gamma irradiation, ethylene oxide (EtO), and vaporized hydrogen peroxide plasma. Each presents distinct challenges, summarized in

4.3 Regulatory Classification and Approval Pathways

The function of the coating determines the regulatory classification of coated devices. Medical device regulations usually apply to devices with coatings that only enhance mechanical or biocompatibility characteristics [Sanyal et al. \(2024a\)](#). On the other hand, coatings that contain pharmacologically active ingredients, like nitric oxide donors or antibiotics, might be governed as combination products, falling under the purview of both medication and device regulatory procedures. Heparin-coated cardiovascular devices and orthopedic implants that elute rifampin and gentamicin are two examples.

Table 9 summarizes key regulatory considerations relevant to biomedical coatings.

Table 9. Regulatory considerations for biomedical coatings.

Aspect	Regulatory Expectations
Biocompatibility	Compliance with ISO 10993 for cytotoxicity, sensitization, irritation, systemic toxicity, and degradation products.
Coating Integrity	Demonstration of adhesion strength, mechanical durability, and particulate generation risk under simulated use conditions.
Sterilization Validation	Proof that coating properties remain intact after sterilization; validation of sterilization efficacy.
Drug Release (if applicable)	Characterization of release kinetics, local/systemic concentrations, and safety profiles.
Efficacy Claims	Evidence to support antimicrobial or biological claims, potentially including clinical data.
Labeling	Disclosure of potential allergens, active agents, and any contraindications.
Manufacturing Consistency	Quality control demonstrating batch-to-batch uniformity in coating thickness and coverage.
Post-Market Surveillance	Plans to monitor for resistance development, coating degradation, or adverse events post-approval.

4.4 Regulatory Successes and Future Directions

Clinical success and regulatory approval have been attained by a number of covered devices. Heparin-coated stents and oxygenators, silver-coated orthopedic prostheses for high-risk revision procedures, and antibacterial central venous catheters coated with chlorhexidine and silver sulfadiazine are a few examples. Comprehensive safety and efficacy demonstrations, including stability tests and leachables analysis, were necessary for these results. In order to keep an eye out for things like bacterial adaptability, post-market surveillance is still essential [Pereira-Silva et al. \(2025b\)](#).

5 Emerging Trends and Future Directions

Multifunctional biomedical coatings that actively influence biological responses and dynamically adapt to their surroundings in addition to providing passive protection have been made possible by recent developments in surface engineering. The creation of stimuli-responsive coatings, which can release growth factors, nitric oxide, or antibacterial compounds in response to physiological

cues like pH, temperature, enzymes, or electrical fields, is a primary emphasis. This allows for localized therapy with minimal systemic consequences. While smart zwitterionic and PEGylated surfaces combine antifouling, hemocompatibility, and osteointegration properties into a single multifunctional platform, nanomaterial-based coatings that incorporate graphene oxide, MOFs, or metallic nanoclusters improve surface area, mechanical strength, and release kinetics Nilawar et al. (2021a).

In parallel, bioinspired and hybrid strategies are using natural mechanisms—like adhesion inspired by mussels, antimicrobial peptides, and patterns taken from extracellular matrix—to imitate biological surfaces, enhance cell adhesion, alter immune responses, and fend against microbial invasion. These three convergent approaches are depicted in the figure, which are produced by techniques such as laser ablation to create metallic or lipid nanoparticles, nanotubes, and nanorods; and bioinspired coatings, which are made by combining metal ions with biological materials to improve biocompatibility and functionality Sanyal et al. (2024b). The next generation of intelligent, adaptable biomedical coatings, designed for orthopedic, cardiovascular, and brain implants, is being shaped by these strategies taken together Pereira-Silva et al. (2025a).

Figure 4. Future Direction of Biomedical coatings

6 Conclusions

Biomedical coatings appear to be an essential strategy for improving several aspects in the application of biomedical devices such as improving the safety, functionality and durability of implants and medical devices. Throughout this work it has been shown that they can be classified into three main categories: antimicrobial, anti-fouling and anti-corrosion, each of these differs in itself so that they also have specific mechanisms that respond to particular clinical needs. Of these three types of coatings we can see them in different ways, for example, antimicrobial coatings prevent bacterial colonization and biofilm formation, on the other hand, anti-fouling minimizes the adhesion of proteins and cells through physical and chemical barriers, which is essential for these, and finally, anti-corrosion coatings protect implantable metals from chemical degradation and the release of ions.

On the other hand, it can also be determined that one of the most important parts is the choice of the type of coating and the deposition method is critical, since this will directly affect adhesion, uniformity, durability, antimicrobial efficiency and anti-fouling properties. Physical techniques such as PVD and CVD offer thin, adherent and precise layers, while chemical and solution methods

such as sol-gel, dip-coating and LbL allow integration of nanoparticles and multifunctionality. In addition, different emerging methods such as electrospinning and ALD have been discussed, which provide control over nanostructures and controlled release of active agents, opening opportunities for smart and adaptive coatings in a more efficient way.

On the other hand, it is also important to mention the conclusions regarding how performance metrics play a central role in evaluating the efficacy of coatings. On the one hand, we were able to see how mechanical adhesion, surface roughness, contact angle, hemocompatibility, biofilm inhibition, corrosion resistance, and osseointegration are very important parameters that guide both the development and clinical selection of coatings for more precise device functionality. Furthermore, biocompatibility, sterilization compatibility, and regulatory compliance are essential requirements for the clinical translation of these materials.

Finally, the most recent advances in multifunctional and intelligent coatings show great potential to enhance the production of biomedical devices in a more effective, practical and durable way. It can be said that these bio-inspired strategies, stimulus-sensitive coatings (pH, temperature, enzymes) and the incorporation of nanomaterials allow dynamic control of the release of antimicrobial agents, antifouling and anticorrosion properties, promoting localized therapies and minimizing systemic effects.

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8 Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- T. D. Andreeva and et al. Composite polymer/wax coatings as a corrosion barrier of bioresorbable magnesium coronary stents. *Heliyon*, 10(13): e34025, Jul 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e34025. [Online]. Available: [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(24\)10056-4](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(24)10056-4): :text=Magnesium
- W. Bäumlner et al. Antimicrobial coatings for environmental surfaces in hospitals. *Critical Reviews in Microbiology*, 48(5):631–650, 2022. doi: 10.1080/1040841X.2021.1991271.
- N. Bharadishettar, B. K., and D. Panemangalore. Coating technologies for copper based antimicrobial active surfaces: A perspective review. *Metals*, 11:711, 2021. doi: 10.3390/MET11050711.
- J. Butler. Review of antimicrobial nanocoatings in medicine and dentistry. *ACS Nano*, 17(12): 11234–11259, 2023. doi: 10.1021/acsnano.2c12488.
- D. Campoccia, L. Montanaro, and C. Arciola. The significance of infection related to orthopedic devices and issues of antibiotic resistance. *Biomaterials*, 34:8015–8027, 2013.
- Q. Chen, S. Liang, and G. Thouas. Elastomeric biomaterials for tissue engineering. *Progress in Polymer Science*, 107:101278, 2020.
- S. Chen, L. Li, C. Zhao, and J. Zheng. Surface hydration: principles and applications toward low-fouling/nonfouling biomaterials. *Polymer*, 51:5283–5293, 2010.
- S. Dorozhkin. Calcium orthophosphate coatings on metals, ceramics, plastics and composites. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine*, 21:1–27, 2010.
- E. Dube and G. E. Okuthe. Silver nanoparticle-based antimicrobial coatings: Sustainable strategies for microbial contamination control. 16(6):110, Jun 2025. doi: 10.3390/microbiolres16060110.
- R. L. Dávalos Monteiro. *Assessing durability of commercial powder coatings: Effects of corrosion testing procedures on corrosion indicators and coating microstructure*. Phd thesis, The

- University of Manchester, 2021. URL <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/assessing-durability-of-commercial-powder-coatings-effects-of-cor/>.
- E. Falde, S. Yohe, Y. Colson, and M. Grinstaff. Superhydrophobic materials for biomedical applications. *Biomaterials*, 104:87–103, 2016.
- A. Grill. Diamond-like carbon: state of the art. *Diamond and Related Materials*, 8:428–434, 1999.
- T. Hanawa. Metal ion release from metal implants. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 31:1385–1395, 2011.
- E. Hetrick and M. Schoenfisch. Reducing implant-related infections: active release strategies. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 35:780–789, 2006.
- H. Huang, S. Singh, A. Juhasz, A. Roccisano, A. Ang, and N. Stanford. Influence of copper distribution in thermally sprayed cu-bearing coatings on corrosion and microbial activity. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2024.130430.
- I. Ielo, F. Giacobello, A. Castellano, S. Sfameni, G. Rando, and M. Plutino. Development of antibacterial and antifouling innovative and eco-sustainable sol-gel based materials: From marine areas protection to healthcare applications. *Gels*, 8, 2021. doi: 10.3390/gels8010026.
- S. Li, P. Huang, Z. Ye, Y. Wang, W. Wang, D. Kong, J. Zhang, L. Deng, and A. Dong. Layer-by-layer zwitterionic modification of diverse substrates with durable anti-corrosion and anti-fouling properties. *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, 2019. doi: 10.1039/c9tb01337g.
- X. Liu, Y.-Y. Lee, J. Zhu, and et al. Zwitterionic coatings for antifouling in medical devices. *Advanced Healthcare Materials*, 3:42–59, 2014.
- Y. Lu, L. Huang, M. Liu, G. Yang, and C. Li. Estructura estratificada heterogénea en recubrimientos de barrera térmica mediante deposición física de vapor por pulverización de plasma. *Journal of Advanced Ceramics*, 2023. doi: 10.26599/jac.2023.9220692.
- S. Mahyoub, A. Farid, M. Azeem, D. Fadhil, F. Qaraah, and Q. Drmosh. Técnicas de deposición física de vapor para la electrorreducción de co: Una revisión. *Small Structures*, 6, 2025. doi: 10.1002/ssstr.202400501.
- H. Mamgain, J. Pandey, and R. Brajpuriya. Aqua barrier: Polypropylene/stearic acid-infused zn-zno-cu multilayer superhydrophobic coatings on steel for enhancing anti-microbial and anti-corrosion efficiency. *ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology*, 2024. doi: 10.1149/2162-8777/ad9631.
- I. Negut, C. Albu, and B. Bitá. Advances in antimicrobial coatings for preventing infections of head-related implantable medical devices. *Coatings*, 14(3):256, 2024. doi: 10.3390/coatings14030256.
- S. Nilawar, P. Sharma, S. Kulkarni, and A. Rao. Emerging trends in bioactive ceramic coatings and surface engineering. *Materials Advances*, 2(18):5882–5895, 2021a. doi: 10.1039/D1MA00733E. URL <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/2021/ma/d1ma00733e>.
- S. Nilawar et al. Emerging trends in bioactive ceramic coatings and surface engineering. *Materials Advances*, 2(18):5882–5895, 2021b. doi: 10.1039/D1MA00733E.
- A. Owhal, A. Pingale, S. Khan, S. Belgamwar, P. Jha, and J. Rathore. Facile and scalable co-deposition of anti-bacterial zn-gns nanocomposite coatings for hospital facilities: Tribo-mechanical and anti-corrosion properties. *JOM*, 73:4270–4278, 2021. doi: 10.1007/s11837-021-04968-5.
- P. Pereira-Silva, A. Silva, R. Costa, L. Ferreira, and J. Santos. Recent advances in metal-based antimicrobial coatings (2021–2023). *Progress in Materials Science*, 137:101254, 2025a. doi: 10.1016/j.pmatsci.2025.101254. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0001868625002015>.
- P. Pereira-Silva et al. Recent advances in metal-based antimicrobial coatings (2021–2023). *Progress in Materials Science*, 137:101254, 2025b. doi: 10.1016/j.pmatsci.2025.101254.

- K. Prime and G. Whitesides. Self-assembled organic monolayers: model systems for studying adsorption of proteins at surfaces. *Science*, 252:1164–1167, 1991.
- H. Qian, Z. Ye, L. Pi, and J. Ao. Roles and current applications of s-nitrosoglutathione in anti-infective biomaterials. *Materials Today Bio*, 16:100419, Sep 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.mtbio.2022.100419.
- E. Rabea, M.-T. Badawy, C. Stevens, G. Smagghe, and W. Steurbaut. Chitosan as antimicrobial agent: applications and mode of action. *Biomacromolecules*, 4:1457–1465, 2003.
- M. Rai, S. Deshmukh, A. Ingle, and A. Gade. Silver nanoparticles: the powerful nanoweapon against multidrug-resistant bacteria. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 112:841–852, 2012.
- B. Ratner, A. Hoffman, F. Schoen, and J. Lemons. *Biomaterials Science: An Introduction to Materials in Medicine*. Elsevier, 3rd edition, 2013.
- S. Sanyal, S. Park, R. Chelliah, S.-J. Yeon, K. Barathikannan, S. Vijayalakshmi, Y.-J. Jeong, M. Rubab, and D. H. Oh. Emerging trends in smart self-healing coatings: A focus on micro/nanocontainer technologies for enhanced corrosion protection. *Coatings*, 14(3):324, 2024a. doi: 10.3390/coatings14030324.
- S. Sanyal, S. Park, R. Chelliah, S.-J. Yeon, K. Barathikannan, S. Vijayalakshmi, Y.-J. Jeong, M. Rubab, and D. H. Oh. Emerging trends in smart self-healing coatings: A focus on micro/nanocontainer technologies for enhanced corrosion protection. *Coatings*, 14(3):324, 2024b. doi: 10.3390/coatings14030324. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-6412/14/3/324>.
- A. Shea. A review of recent progress in synthetic polymer surface coatings. *Molecules*, 30(13): 2710, 2025. doi: 10.3390/molecules30132710.
- R. Teixeira-Santos, M. Lima, L. C. Gomes, and F. J. Mergulhão. Antimicrobial coatings based on chitosan to prevent implant-associated infections: A systematic review. *iScience*, 24(12): 103480, Nov 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2021.103480.
- M. Tian, Z. Lin, W. Tang, W. Wu, L. Wang, and J. Zhang. Electrophoretic deposition of tetracycline loaded bioactive glasses/chitosan as antibacterial and bioactive composite coatings on magnesium alloys. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2023.107841.
- M. Yaseen, M. Khattak, A. Khan, S. Bibi, M. Bououdina, M. Usman, N. Khan, A. Pirzado, R. Abumousa, and M. Humayun. Dispositivos de película delgada electrocrómica de última generación, técnicas de fabricación y aplicaciones: una revisión. *Nanocomposites*, 10:1–40, 2023. doi: 10.1080/20550324.2023.2291619.
- Z. K. Zander and M. L. Becker. Antimicrobial and antifouling strategies for polymeric medical devices. *ACS Macro Letters*, 7(1):16–25, Jan 2018. doi: 10.1021/acsmacrolett.7b00879. Epub 2017 Dec 14.
- L. Zhang, Z. Cao, T. Bai, and et al. Zwitterionic hydrogels implanted in mice resist the foreign-body reaction. *Nature Biotechnology*, 37:1362–1370, 2019a.
- Q. Zhang, D. Geng, and W. Hu. Deposición química de vapor para materiales bidimensionales de pocas capas. *SmartMat*, 4, 2023. doi: 10.1002/smm2.1177.
- S. Zhang, X. Liang, G. Gadd, and Q. Zhao. Advanced titanium dioxide-polytetrafluorethylene (tio2-ptfe) nanocomposite coatings on stainless steel surfaces with antibacterial and anti-corrosion properties. *Applied Surface Science*, 2019b. doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.06.070.
- S. Zhang, X. Liang, G. Gadd, and Q. Zhao. A sol-gel based silver nanoparticle/polytetrafluorethylene (agnp/ptfe) coating with enhanced antibacterial and anti-corrosive properties. *Applied Surface Science*, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.147675.